

MODELING AND PREDICTION OF RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF POLYMER COMPOSITES EXPOSED TO HEAT

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ABSTRACT

Composites are increasingly utilized in structural applications for military and commercial aircraft due to their high specific strength and stiffness. Despite these advantages over metal components, there is a significant risk if these structures are exposed to fires or high-temperature exhaust gas impingement. After an elevated temperature exposure, the composite properties may be significantly compromised even if minimal visible damage is apparent. Consequently, it is desired to have a rapid heat damage assessment and failure prediction tool based on operational and inspection data. This paper presents our efforts on developing models and simulation tools to predict residual strength of carbon/epoxy composites exposed to heat. A thermal decomposition kinetic model was developed based on the thermogravimetric data for the 5320-1 composite material. The residual short beam shear (SBS) strength of the composite was measured and related to the mass loss of the samples subjected to isothermal heating. Based on these results, a residual strength model was developed to predict the residual SBS strength of composite exposed to heat. The model has been validated and used to simulate degradation of carbon/epoxy composites subjected to isothermal heating. In addition, it was shown that the kinetic model derived for 5320-1 composites may be used with the residual strength data of other carbon/epoxy composites to develop a residual strength model for those composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aircraft polymer composite components are often exposed to extreme temperatures due to thermal events including exhaust impingement, engine fires, fuel fires, equipment overheating, brake fires, and lightning strikes. During thermal exposure, a chemical change in the matrix can occur and results in a reduction of composite mechanical properties. These chemical changes are difficult to detect with traditional Nondestructive Inspection (NDI) techniques (hardness, ultrasonic, visual inspection). This is classified as incipient heat damage. While some experimental methods such as Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) technique may be used to inspect and disposition incipient heat damage on composite structures [1], development of a multi-physics model is desired to predict the structural response for a given temporal and spatial evolution of thermal environment.

To predict the post-fire mechanical response of single skin, flat composite laminates, Gibson et al. [2] proposed a model to predict the residual strength of polymer composites assuming the material has 100% and 0% strength left for the charred and uncharred portions of the material, respectively. Mouritz et al. [3, 4] proposed a simple two-layer model, one for the thermally affected region to have reduced or zero mechanical properties and a completely undamaged region with original mechanical properties. These models do not consider the property degradation in the resin decomposition region and cannot predict the residual strength of composites with incipient heat damage.

The goal of the present work is to develop a tool to predict residual strength of carbon/epoxy composites after a known time and temperature event. The time at temperature is such that the strength degradation is detectable whereas the physical damage (delamination) has not occurred yet. This is the region of highest interest for predictive capability and the focus of our efforts in this project. The mechanical property evaluation is focused on matrix sensitive short beam shear (SBS) strength test.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Cycom 5320-1 prepreg (T650-35 3K plain weave fabric with resin content of 36%) manufactured by Solvay was used for making composites with single vacuum bag process. According to the manufacturer, Cycom 5320-1 is a toughened epoxy resin prepreg system designed for vacuum-bag-only (VBO) or out of autoclave (OOA) manufacturing of primary structural parts. The 5320-1 composites are also supported by an extensive set of multi batch mechanical and physical property databases [5].

2.2 Methods

Laminate and Test Coupon Preparation. Composite panels were fabricated using 16 pies of prepreg with single vacuum bag process cured in a convection oven with curing cycle recommended by the prepreg manufacturer. The cured panel has thickness of 0.122 inches. The panels were machined to generate test coupons with nominal dimension of 0.75"×0.25"×0.125" for thermal aging, mass loss and SBS tests. The coupons were dried at 80°C for 48 hours in a convection oven before used in the following treatments. The mass of dried samples was measured and used to calculate the mass loss of the composite after thermal aging.

Thermal Aging. Thermal aging of composite samples (SBS test coupons) was performed in a convection oven (Heratherm OMH60). A mineral wool insulation sheet was mounted in front of oven chamber to minimize the temperature drop when the oven door was opened. A small opening (3" × 1") was cut out on the sheet to allow the samples passing through the sheet. Two types of heating — isothermal heating and constant rate heating — were performed for thermal aging. To conduct the constant rate heating, heat oven to 50°C first, place composite samples (6 SBS test coupons as a set) in the oven and close the door. The oven was heated to target temperatures at the set heating rate. The samples were taken out of the oven when the target temperature was reached. The mass of aged samples was measured when the samples were cooled down.

Mass Loss Measurement. After heat exposure, the mass of the coupons was measured with balance with precision of 0.0001g. The mass loss of the samples is equal to the difference between the mass of the samples before and after heat exposure.

Short Beam Shear (SBS) Test. Short beam shear test for the aged samples was performed at room temperature on ADMET Expert 2611 Tester based on ASTM D2344 standard. The displacement rate was 0.05 inches/minute. Five specimens were evaluated to get average strength for each set of samples.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mass Loss and Kinetic Model of Composites

Mass Loss of the Composites. Mass loss (%) of 5320-1 composites (SBS coupons) subjected to isothermal heating and constant rate heating is shown in Figure 1(a) and (b), respectively. The mass loss (%) is defined as $(m_0 - m) / m_0 \times 100\%$, where m_0 and m are original mass and instantaneous mass at t , respectively. In general, mass loss depends on the aging time and temperature for isothermal heating. The higher temperature or longer time, the greater the mass loss values. For constant rate heating, the lower the heating rate, the greater the mass loss values. It is thus believed that mass loss can be a good indicator for severity of incipient heat damage of the composites.

Kinetic Model. According to the literature, the model or a mathematical description of the mass loss data is usually sought in terms of a 'kinetic triplet' (i.e., Arrhenius parameters A and E , and the reaction model, $F(\alpha)$, also called the conversion function) which is related to the experimental data as follows [6]

Figure 1: Mass loss (%) of 5320-1 composites subjected to (a) isothermal and (b) constant rate heating.

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) F(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

where R is gas constant, T is temperature (K), α is the extent of conversion defined as

$$\alpha = (m_i - m) / (m_i - m_f) \quad (2)$$

where m_i , m and m_f are the initial, instantaneous and final mass of the material, respectively. For mass loss data obtained at a constant heating rate $dT/dt = \beta$, $d\alpha/dt$ in Eq.(1) can be replaced with $\beta d\alpha/dT$:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT} = \frac{A}{\beta} \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) F(\alpha) \quad (3)$$

or

$$\ln\left(\beta \frac{d\alpha}{dT}\right) = -\frac{E}{RT} + \ln(A) + \ln(F(\alpha)) \quad (4)$$

For a fixed degree of progress α , the plots of $\ln(\beta d\alpha/dT)$ versus $1/T$ show parallel lines with a slope equal to $-E/R$, which leads to a method known as Friedman method for determining the activation energy E in the literature [7]. To get the α data, one needs not only initial and instantaneous mass of the material, but also the final mass of the material. If the final mass is not available or applicable, a fraction of mass loss α^* as defined in

$$\alpha^* = (m_i - m) / m_i \quad (5)$$

may be used. Let

$$\lambda = m_i / (m_i - m_f) \quad (6)$$

we have

$$\alpha^* = \alpha / \lambda \quad (7)$$

With α being replaced with $\lambda\alpha^*$, Eq.(1) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{d\alpha^*}{dt} = A^* \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) f(\alpha^*) \quad (8)$$

where A^* ($=A/\lambda$) and $f(\alpha^*)$ represent the pre-exponential parameter and reaction model corresponding to α^* . From this equation it follows that

$$\ln\left(\beta \frac{d\alpha^*}{dT}\right) = -\frac{E}{RT} + \ln(A^*) + \ln(f(\alpha^*)) \quad (9)$$

Comparing Eq.(9) and Eq.(4), it is apparent that the activation energy E can also be determined from $d\alpha^*/dT$. Figure 2 shows $\ln \alpha^*$ as a function of temperature for 5320-1 composites subjected to constant

rate heating. As seen in the figure, $d \ln \alpha^*/dT$ is a constant at a fixed heating rate, it is thus more convenient to use $d \ln \alpha^*/dT$ instead of $d\alpha^*/dT$ for the calculation. Rewrite Eq.(9) as

Figure 2: $\ln \alpha^*$ as a function of temperature for 5320-1 composites subjected to constant rate heating. Closed circles represent measured data, dotted lines represent model predicted values.

$$\ln \left(\beta \frac{d \ln(\alpha^*)}{dT} \right) = -\frac{E}{RT} + \ln(A^*) + \ln(f(\alpha^*)) - \ln(\alpha^*) \quad (10)$$

then the activation energy E can be determined from plots of $\ln(\beta d \ln \alpha^*/dT)$ versus $1/T$ at fixed α^* levels. The result can be represented by

$$E = a \ln \alpha^* + b = 19.22 \ln \alpha^* + 230.92 \text{ (kJ/mol)} \quad (11)$$

From Eqs.(10)-(11) and the mass loss data, $f(\alpha^*) = \alpha^{*n}$ (where n is a constant) and A^* can be determined, Eq.(8) thus becomes

$$\frac{d\alpha^*}{dt} = A^* \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) \alpha^{*n} \quad (12)$$

Integration of Eq.(12) gives the α^* of the composites subjected to isothermal heating

$$\alpha^* = \left[A^* k \exp\left(-\frac{b}{RT}\right) (t - t_0) + (\alpha^*_0)^k \right]^{1/k} \quad (13)$$

where α^*_0 is α^* at t_0 and $k = a/(RT) - n + 1$, a and b are defined in Eq.(11). Given t_0 (=15 min) and α^*_0 , the mass loss of composite at any time $t > t_0$ and T can be predicted using this equation. For composites subjected to constant rate heating, the mass loss becomes

$$\alpha^* = \alpha^*_0 \exp \left[\frac{A^*}{\beta} \exp\left(-\frac{E_0}{RT_0}\right) (\alpha^*_0)^{n-1} (T - T_0) \right] \quad (14)$$

where α^*_0 is α^* at T_0 and E_0 is the activation energy at $\alpha^* = \alpha^*_0$. The mass loss predicted using Eq.(14) and $T_0 = 260^\circ\text{C}$ is presented in Figure 2. As seen in the figure, the calculated values are in very good agreement with measured data for all heating rates and temperatures. The mass loss values calculated from Eq.(13) (data are not presented here) also agree with the measured data for the samples subjected to isothermal heating.

3.2 SBS Strength of Composites

Short beam shear strength of 5320-1 composites subjected to isothermal heating is given in Figure 3. Figure 4 shows the plots of SBS reduction versus mass loss for 5320-1 composites subjected to isothermal heating. Apparently, the relationship between SBS reduction and mass loss for a fixed aging

time (15, 30, 60 and 120 minutes) can be represented by a linear equation. This means that, given exposure/aging time, the SBS strength reduction is proportional to the mass loss of the material.

Figure 3: Short beam shear strength of 5320-1 composites subjected to isothermal heating.

The slope of lines was plotted against exposure time in Figure 5. The data can be fitted by a power law equation $y = 205.24x^{-0.452}$. Combining the results obtained from Figs.(4) and (5), we have:

$$\frac{\Delta F}{F_0} = ct^d \frac{\Delta M}{M_0} = 205.24t^{-0.452}\alpha^* \quad (15)$$

where $\Delta F = F_0 - F$, $\Delta M = M_0 - M$, M_0 and F_0 are the original mass and SBS strength of the material (no heat exposure), M and F represent the mass and SBS strength of the composite exposed to heat for t minutes.

Figure 4: Plots of SBS strength reduction versus mass loss of 5320-1 composites subjected to isothermal heating with aging times indicated.

Figure 5: The plot of slope of lines in Figure 4 versus aging time.

3.3 Residual Strength Models for 5320-1 Composites

Based on the above equations, models have been developed to predict the residual SBS strength of the composites subjected to isothermal heating. From

$$F = F_0 \left(1 - \frac{\Delta F}{F_0} \right) \quad (16)$$

it follows that

$$F = F_0 \left\{ 1 - ct^d \left[A^* k \text{Exp} \left(-\frac{b}{RT} \right) (t - t_0) + (a^*_0)^k \right]^{1/k} \right\} \quad (17)$$

To verify/validate the residual strength models, the residual strength of 5320-1 composites subjected to isothermal heating were calculated from Eq.(17). The results together with the testing data are presented in Figure 6. As seen in the figure, the measured and predicted residual strengths are in very good agreement for all aging temperatures and times or heating rates. In fact, the predicted values are within the error bars of measured data in most cases. In other words, the difference between predicted and measured strength values are generally within the experimental errors. The result confirmed that the residual strength model works well for the composites.

Figure 6: Comparison of model predicted and measured short beam strength for 5320-1 composites subjected to isothermal heating at 220~280°C for (a) 15, (b) 30, (c) 60 and (d) 120 minutes.

3.4 Residual Strength Prediction for Other Composites

A novel residual strength model has been developed and demonstrated successfully for short beam strength of CYCOM 5320-1 composite system. As lots of experimental work is needed to establish the residual strength models, a model or method is desired for prediction of residual strength of general carbon/epoxy composites (not limited to 5320-1) with no or minimal amount of experimental work required.

It was noticed that there were residual strength data sets (such as SBS, flexural and/or compressive strength data) for various carbon/epoxy composites exposed to heat with exposure conditions reported in the literature (see [8] for example). We have tried to “predict” the residual strength of the materials using our model (for 5320-1 composites) and then compare the result with the testing data to see how our model works for those materials. While good agreement between “predicted” and tested data was seen in some cases, poor results were observed in most cases. This means our model may not be

applicable to other materials in general. However, if our model is adapted to the new material and property first, it is possible to predict residual strength of the material without need for additional experiments. Below we will explain this further with some examples.

Figure 7(a) and (b) present the SBS strength reduction of dry and wet IM6/3501-6 carbon fiber/epoxy composites (data obtained from Ref [8]) versus mass loss of CYCOM 5320-1 exposed to heat with condition given in Ref [8], respectively. As seen in the figure, for either dry or wet samples, the SBS strength reduction of IM6/3501-6 and mass loss of dry 5320-1 composite can be represented by a linear equation as shown in the following equation:

$$\frac{\Delta F}{F_0} = c_x \alpha^*_s \quad (18)$$

where $\Delta F = F_0 - F$, F_0 and F are the original and instantaneous SBS strength of IM6/3501-6, α^*_s represents the mass loss of dry 5320-1 composite exposed to heat (obtained from Eq.(13)), c_x is the slope of the line which equals to 25.743 and 35.912 for the dry and wet IM6/3501-6 samples, respectively. Eq.(19) gives the residual SBS strength model (adapted model) for IM6/3501-6 subjected to isothermal heating

$$F = F_0(1 - c_x \alpha^*_s) = F_0 \left\{ 1 - c_x \left[A^* k \text{Exp} \left(-\frac{b}{RT} \right) (t - t_0) + (\alpha^*_0)^k \right]^{1/k} \right\} \quad (19)$$

where the expression for α^*_s was from Eq.(13). The measured and model predicted SBS strength of dry and wet IM6/3501-6 composites are shown in Figure 7(c) and (d), respectively. As seen in the figures, the model predicted and measured SBS strengths are in excellent agreement.

Figure 7: SBS strength reduction of dry (a) and wet (b) IM6/3501-6 carbon/epoxy composites versus mass loss of CYCOM 5320-1 exposed to heat. Comparison of measured and model predicted SBS strength of dry (c) and wet (d) IM6/3501-6 composites exposed to heat.

Similar results were obtained for residual flexural strength of IM6/3501-6 composites (Figure 8) with testing data obtained from Ref [8] as well. As seen in the figure, the flexural strength reduction of IM6/3501-6 and mass loss of dry 5320-1 composite can be represented by a linear equation, with slope being 32.819 and 31.315 for the dry and wet samples, respectively. A residual flexural strength model

can be derived for dry or wet IM6/3501-6 composites. As shown in Figure 8(c) and (d), the model predicted flexural strengths are in very good agreement with the testing data.

In summary, the adapted model can be derived by a) plotting strength reduction ($\Delta F/ F_0$) against mass loss (α^*_s) of 5320-1, b) finding relation $\Delta F/ F_0 = f(\alpha^*_s)$ ($= c_x \alpha^*_s$ in above examples) and, c) getting residual strength $F = F_0 [1 - f(\alpha^*_s)]$.

Figure 8: Flexural strength reduction of dry (a) and wet (b) IM6/3501-6 carbon/epoxy composites versus mass loss of CYCOM 5320-1 exposed to heat. Comparison of measured and model predicted flexural strength of dry (c) and wet (d) IM6/3501-6 composites exposed to heat.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Efforts have been made to model and simulate the incipient heat damage of carbon/epoxy composites exposed to excessive heat. A decomposition kinetic model has been developed based on the non-isothermal thermogravimetric data for the composite coupons for short beam shear (SBS) test. The result shows that the decomposition reaction can be represented by a power law model, and the reaction model may be determined without presuming the form of the model beforehand. The kinetic model has been verified using both non-isothermal and isothermal thermogravimetric data. The model predicted mass loss values are in excellent agreement with the experimental data. A quantitative relationship was established between mass loss and short beam shear (SBS) strength reduction of the composites subjected to isothermal heating. Based on the relationship and the kinetic model, a residual strength model has been developed to predict the residual strength of composites. The residual SBS strength of composites exposed to heat was measured and compared with the model predicted data. The result showed that the model predicted and measured strengths are in excellent agreement. In addition, the kinetic model derived for 5320-1 composites may be used with the residual strength data of other carbon/epoxy composites to establish a residual strength model for those composites.

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